

Date Accessed (of search)	Search (Search term used)	Origin of website (e.g. Knowledge of Researcher; found in X)	(Primary) Website	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social)	High level finding (data we are interested in)	National; Regional or Cantonal	Experts Identified	Experts Note	New Website Identified	Website TYPE 1	Website TYPE 2 (i.e. Field Health; Social Care; Education; Youth work etc. See list)	Note	New Website Identified - Used as search?
24.01.2018	young carers legislation	Google Search	https://professionals.carers.org/new-rights-young-carers-england	NGO	Carer organ	The Children and Families Act and Care Act 2014, which come into force in April 2015, significantly strengthens the rights of young carers.	National	-	-	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	NGO information	Carer organisations	overview of new legislation in England	y
24.01.2018	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	https://professionals.carers.org/new-rights-young-carers-england	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	NGO	Carer organ	The Children and Families Act 2014 is an important new piece of legislation for young carers, young adult carers and their families. It amends Section 17 of the Children Act 1989, introducing sections 17ZA, 17ZB and 17ZC. Carers Trust along with many Carers Trust Network Partners and the National Young Carers Coalition campaigned for these rights. They work alongside another piece of legislation, the Care Act 2014, which creates rights for young carers who provide care or support to an adult. The Care Act 2014, explained in this briefing from Carers Trust, also creates the right to a young carer's transition assessment during a young carer's transition to adulthood. Together the two pieces of legislation require local authorities to use a whole-family approach. This briefing summarises the key points in the Children and Families Act 2014 primary legislation and The Young Carers (Needs Assessments) Regulations 2015. Please note that this document is not intended as a full briefing on the law.1	National	-	-	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted	UK Government	UK Government		y
24.01.2018	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/6/section/96/enacted?view=plain	UK Government	-	-	-
24.01.2018	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/section/63/enacted	UK Government	-	-	May have missed important information [I did using a search like this]
24.01.2018	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted	UK Government	UK Government	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/section/63/enacted	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Transition Assessments fro young carers
24.01.2018	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/6/section/96/enacted?view=plain	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/6/section/96/enacted?view=plain	UK Government	UK Government	Children and Families Act 2014: Young carers UPDATING In the Children Act 1989, after section 17 insert— "17ZA : Young carers' needs assessments: England	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Updatint of Children Act 1989
24.01.2018	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	https://professionals.carers.org/sites/default/files/children_and_families_act_briefing.pdf	UK Government	UK Government	CHILDREN AND YOUNG PERSONS, ENGLAND The Young Carers (Needs Assessments) Regulations 2015	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Regulatinos for Young carers needs assessment
06.02.18	young carers legal provisions scotland [when searching for Scotland]	Google Search	https://www.carersuk.org/help-and-advice/practical-support/getting-care-and-support/young-carers-and-carers-of-children-under-19	NGO	Carer organisations	Young carers Young carers are children under 18 with caring responsibilities, and their rights to be assessed come mostly from the Children Act 1989 and the Children and Families Act 2014. If there is an adult being looked after, then the local council has a duty to consider whether there are any children involved in providing care, and if so, what the impact is on that child. The local council have a duty to assess 'on the appearance of need' (ie without a 'request' having to be made). They also have a more general duty to 'take reasonable steps' to identify young carers in their area. The local council must involve the child with caring responsibilities, their parents and any other person the young carer requests in the assessment process. The	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

12.02.18	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/care-act-statutory-guidance/care-and-support-statutory-guidance	https://childlawadvice.org.uk/information-pages/young-carers/	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/care-act-statutory-guidance/care-and-support-statutory-guidance	UK Government	UK Government	<p>Guidance:</p> <p>1. Care and support statutory guidance: Whole family approach</p> <p>6.65 The intention of the whole family approach is for local authorities to take a holistic view of the person's needs and to identify how the adult's needs for care and support impact on family members or others in their support network. : See also 6.65 - 6.73</p> <p>2. 16. Transition to adult care and support</p> <p>This chapter provides guidance on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sections 58 to 66 of the Care Act The Care and Support (Children's Carers) Regulations 2014. <p>This chapter covers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> when a transition assessment must be carried out adult carers and young carers <p>Adult carers and young carers 16.21 - 16.24</p>	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Whole Family Approach See also 6.65 - 6.73 : SECTION 63 (Transition Assessments - not visible)	-
12.02.18	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/527/made	https://childlawadvice.org.uk/information-pages/young-carers/	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/527/made	UK Government	UK Government	<p>CHILDREN AND YOUNG PERSONS, ENGLAND</p> <p>The Young Carers (Needs Assessments) Regulations 2015</p>	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	Archive regulations	-
12.02.18	young carers legal provisions England	Google Search	https://www.carersuk.org/help-and-advice/practical-support/getting-care-and-support/young-carers-and-carers-of-children-under-18	NGO	Carer organisations	<p>Young carers are children under 18 with caring responsibilities, and their rights to be assessed come mostly from the Children Act 1989 and the Children and Families Act 2014.</p> <p>If there is an adult being looked after, then the local council has a duty to consider whether there are any children involved in providing care, and if so, what the impact is on that child.</p> <p>The local council have a duty to assess 'on the appearance of need' (ie without a 'request' having to be made). They also have a more general duty to 'take reasonable steps' to identify young carers in their area.</p> <p>The local council must involve the child with caring responsibilities, their parents and any other person the young carer requests in the assessment process. The assessment itself must look at whether or not the young carer wishes to continue caring, and whether it is</p>	-	-	-	-	-	-	Young carers are children under 18 with caring responsibilities, and their rights to be assessed come mostly from the Children Act 1989 and the Children and Families Act 2014	-	
12.02.19	-	-	-	-	-	<p>Transition to adulthood</p> <p>When young carers and disabled children are approaching 18 there are different provisions in place.</p> <p>Young carers become entitled to a Young Carer's assessment 'in transition'. Disabled children become entitled to a Child's Needs Assessments 'in transition'. Carers of disabled children (either with or without parental responsibility) become entitled to a Child's Carer's Assessment 'in transition'.</p> <p>These assessments must be carried out by the local council where it considers that the young carer, disabled child or carer of a disabled child is likely to have care and support needs after the child becomes 18 and there is 'significant benefit' to the young carer, disabled child or adult carer if an assessment is carried out.</p> <p>You can read more about transition assessments in our assessments factsheet.</p>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
-	-	-	-	-	-	Charging for services received under the Children Act 1989	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.02.18	young carers legal provisions England	Google Search	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/social-care-and-support/young-carers-rights/	National Health Service	Health	<p>1. The law is changing for young carers, and from April 2015 a social worker from your local authority must visit to carry out a "young carers needs assessment" to decide what kind of help you and your family might need if you or your parents request this. 2. Carers Allowance</p>	National	-	-	-	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/social-care-and-support/carers-allowance/	National Health Service	Health	Carers Allowance	y

12.02.18	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/social-care-and-support/carers-allowance/	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/social-care-and-support/young-carers-rights/	https://www.nhs.uk/conditions/social-care-and-support/carers-allowance/	National Health Service	Health	Carer's Allowance is the main state benefit for carers, so it's important to find out if you can receive it. It is currently £62.70 a week, with a one-off £10 Christmas bonus in December. You might be able to get Carer's Allowance if all of the following apply: you're 16 or over you spend at least 35 hours a week caring for someone you have been in England, Scotland or Wales for at least two of the last three years you normally live in England, Scotland or Wales, or you live abroad as a member of the armed forces you're not in full-time education or studying for more than 21 hours a week you earn less than £116 a week (after taxes, care costs while you're at work and 50% of what you pay into your pension)	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	You can claim Carer's Allowance if you're aged 16 or over.	-
12.02.18	young carers legal provisions England	Google Search	https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/268684/Factsheet_8_update__tweak_.pdf	Government website (National)	Health	The Care Bill – The law for carers (2013)	National	Dame Philippa Russell,	Chair of Standing Commission on Carers	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/reco-gnised-valued-	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Development of carers legislation	y	
12.02.18	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/reco-gnised-valued-and-supported-next-steps-for-the-carers-strategy	https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/268684/Factsheet_8_update__tweak_.pdf	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/reco-gnised-valued-and-supported-next-steps-for-the-carers-strategy	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Carers Stregy (Refreshed) 2010	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
12.02.18	young carers legal provisions England	Google Search	https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/Young%20Carers%20needs%20assessment.pdf	Government website (Local)	Government website (Local)	Young Carers' Needs Assessment. This information has been developed to provide supporting information for the Young Carers Memorandum of Understanding.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	1. The starting point for any assessment will always be – children are children first. 2. ALSO to search 'Care Act and whole family approaches' Document 3. And ADCS Working together to support young carers document 4. And No wrong doors	-
12.02.18	young carers legal provisions England	Google Search	https://www.scie.org.uk/care-act-2014/transition-from-childhood-to-adulthood/young-carer-transition-in-practice/transition-in-care-act-children-and-families-act.asp	Social Care for Excellence	Social care	Transition in the Care Act 2014 and the Children and Families Act 2014	National	-	-	https://www.scie.org.uk/care-act-2014/transition-from-childhood-to-adulthood/young-carer-transition-in-practice/	Social Care for Excellence	Social care	-	y	
12.02.18	https://www.scie.org.uk/care-act-2014/transition-from-childhood-to-adulthood/young-carer-transition-in-practice/	https://www.scie.org.uk/care-act-2014/transition-from-childhood-to-adulthood/young-carer-transition-in-practice/transition-in-care-act-children-and-families-act.asp	https://www.scie.org.uk/care-act-2014/transition-from-childhood-to-adulthood/young-carer-transition-in-practice/	Social Care for Excellence	Social care	1. The Care Act 2014 places a duty on local authorities to conduct transition assessments for children, children's carers and young carers where there is a likely need for care and support after the child in question turns 18 and a transition assessment would be of 'significant benefit' (see below). This resource should be read in conjunction with the statutory guidance underpinning the Act, [1] in particular chapter 16: 'Transition to adult care and support'.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
12.02.18						2. Definition of young carer A young carer is 'a person under 18 who provides or intends to provide care for another person' (Children Act, 1989, section 17ZA(3), as inserted by section 96(1) of the Children and Families Act 2014). For the purposes of transition, a young carer is 'a person under 18 who provides or intends to provide care for an adult' (Care Act 2014, section 63(6)). In both cases, care does not include volunteering or employment in care services, but it does include a young person providing practical support, personal care and/or emotional support to an adult (usually a parent, but it can also be a sibling, grandparent or friend of the family) who may, for example, have a disability, serious illness, or needs relating to old age or as a result of the misuse of substances.	National	-	-	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/care-act-2014-statutory-guidance-for-implementation	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	This publication was withdrawn on 10 March 2016 Superseded by the Care and Support Statutory Guidance	-	

12.02.18										http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	-		y
12.02.18	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted	https://www.scie.org.uk/care-act-2014/transition-from-childhood-to-adulthood/young-carer-transition-in-practice/	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2014/23/contents/enacted	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	63.Assessment of a young carer's needs for support 64.Young carer's assessment: requirements etc.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	63.Assessment of a young carer's needs for support 64.Young carer's assessment: requirements etc.	
12.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	63: Assessment of a young carer's needs for support (1)Where it appears to a local authority that a young carer is likely to have needs for support after becoming 18, the authority must, if it is satisfied that it would be of significant benefit to the young carer to do so and if the consent condition is met, assess— (a)whether the young carer has needs for support and, if so, what those needs are, and (b)whether the young carer is likely to have needs for support after becoming 18 and, if so, what those needs are likely to be.	National	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
12.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	64: Young carer's assessment: requirements etc. (1)A young carer's assessment must include an assessment of— (a)whether the young carer is able to provide care for the person in question and is likely to continue to be able to do so after becoming 18, (b)whether the young carer is willing to do so and is likely to continue to be willing to do so after becoming 18, (c)the impact on the matters specified in section 1(2) of what the young carer's needs for support are likely to be after the young carer becomes 18, (d)the outcomes that the young carer wishes to achieve in day-to-day life, and (e)whether, and if so to what extent, the provision of support could contribute to the achievement of those outcomes.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	65Assessments under sections 58 to 64: further provision	-
12.02.18	Young carers legal provisions England	Google Search	file:///C:/Users/ProBook4340s/Downloads/CBP7219%20(1).pdf	Government website (National)	Government website (National)	Summary This short briefing paper sets out the rights and benefits afforded to carers in law, covering employment rights, protection from discrimination and social security benefits. It also provides information on carers' rights to an assessment of need from their local authority, and what needs can be covered by a carer's assessment, including respite breaks, work, education, training and leisure activities. Significant changes to carers' assessments, and to the rights of young carers and parent carers of disabled children, came into force on 1 April 2015. This is as a result of provisions in the Care Act 2014 and the Children and Families Act 2014, details of which are also provided. As care is a devolved matter, this briefing paper refers to England unless otherwise specified.	National	Barbara Keeley	Barbara Keeley: To ask the Secretary of State for Work and Pensions						1. Carers UK. Estimates on the number of carers missing out on Carer's Allowance, 28 November 2013 2. Government Equalities Office, Equality Act 2010: What do I need to know as a carer?, 2010
12.02.18	https://makingstepchange.info/resources-2/legislation-regulations-guidance/	Researcher Knowledge	https://makingstepchange.info/resources-2/legislation-regulations-guidance/	NGO	Carer organisations	Links to legislation and guidance for young carers	National	-	-	https://makingstepchange.info/resources-2/key-resources/	NGO	Carer organisations	-		y
12.02.18	https://makingstepchange.info/resources-2/key-resources/	https://makingstepchange.info/resources-2/legislation-regulations-guidance/	https://makingstepchange.info/resources-2/key-resources/	NGO	Carer organisations	1. 'Care Act and Whole-Family Approaches' 2. No wrong doors: working together to support young carers and their families 3. Young Carers' Needs Assessment	National	-	-	https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/care-act-and-whole-family-6e1.pdf	Government website (National) (Local) NGOs	Government website (National) (Local) NGOs	-		y
12.02.18	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/no-wrong-doors-working-to-27d.pdf	-	-	-	-	y

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<https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/care-act-and-whole-family-6e1.pdf>

Government website (National) (Local) NGOs

Government website (National) (Local) NGOs
This document aims to provide practical guidance for practitioners working in adult social care in relation to carrying out assessments and developing plans which consider the needs of the whole family. It does not cover all aspects of the Care Act but is intended to assist practitioners to consider how to develop whole-family approaches in line with the new requirements. It also considers how the Act works in tandem with the provisions of the Children and Families Act to create a cohesive legislative framework that allows assessment and support for families to be combined where appropriate. More detailed information on implementing the Care Act is available in statutory guidance¹ and in the suite of best practice guidance² that underpins it, produced mainly by the Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE)³

National

<https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/care-act-and-whole-family-6e1.pdf>

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<https://www.local.gov.uk/sites/default/files/documents/no-wrong-doors-working-to-27d.pdf>

Government website (Local) NGOs

Government website (Local) NGOs
The template in this paper is a resource to help promote working together between Adult's and Children's social care services and enhanced partnership working with health and third sector partners. The final local text may be varied to reflect local circumstances and policies.

National